

Review on Performance of Quick Sort Algorithm

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Abstract: Sorting is an important part of computer science field. Many sorting algorithm available, Quicksort is one of them that based on divide and conquer technique. Quicksort algorithm was published in 1961. Partitioning is the main thing in Quicksort algorithm that done in various way. Pivot is selected in partitioning. The performance of Quicksort depends on selection of pivot. Multiple pivot sort algorithm select many pivot from the array. The performance of multiple pivot sort algorithm is better than single pivot sort. Quicksort perform better result for large dataset and it is cache friendly algorithm. In duplication of elements hybrid approach provide better result than existing quicksort algorithm, Hybrid approach minimize the time complexity when elements are repeated.

Keywords

Sorting, MQ sort, SMS algorithm, Quicksort algorithm, Time complexity, Hybrid Quicksort, Multiple pivot sort

1. Introduction

Quicksort is one of the best algorithm in some situations. It works like a merge sort algorithm. Quicksort recursively call the function for sorting array. The running time of Quicksort for best case and average case is $O(n \lg n)$, and for worst case is $O(n^2)$. If we are doing sorting in ascending order then select a pivot from array. When pivot selected then move all elements greater than pivot right side on the pivot and the elements less than pivot on left side of pivot. When found a elements that is greater than pivot on left side of pivot and other element found less than pivot on right side of pivot then both element are swapped and so on process continue. Divide and concur means array are dived into number of sub arrays, then sub array further divided into number sub arrays. The function or partitioning are recursively called and sort the array.

Simple Quicksort algorithm provide not good result for some situations so used the enhanced quicksort algorithm, multiple pivot sort algorithm and hybrid quick sort algorithm to increase the sorting ability of

Quicksort by using some changes. Enhanced Quicksort algorithm use the concept of SMS (Scan, Move, Sort). If our data set is very large then Enhanced Quicksort algorithm gave good result. When we have large array and some repeated number then Multiple Pivot sort perform better and use less time to sort the array. Hybrid Quicksort algorithm gave good performance when duplicate elements are occur in the many indexes.

2.1 Multiple Pivot Sort Algorithm is Faster than Quick Sort Algorithm: An Empirical Study

The purpose of this paper is to prove that Multiple Pivot Sort algorithm is better than other sorting algorithm through empirical study. Data is sorting in ascending or descending order. The empirical study used different size of sample data (integer, strings) and used different sorting algorithm. The purpose of using different algorithm is to check Time Complexity, number of comparison, number of data move.

In Multiple Pivot Sort Algorithm select 7 to 15 pivots that have same distance, if we have large amount of data. If our pivot is same then between two pivots same pivot placed that is edge point than quick sort. When data is moved end of the list then sort through Insertion sort. Quick sort perform better in average case. Multiple Pivot Sort worst case is $n^2/4$ that is half from quick sort worst case, because we used more pivots that's why less number of comparison and data move used. So the performance of Multiple Pivot Sort is better than Quick Sort Algorithm in worst case. Multiple Pivot sort algorithm used many partition so, sorting accomplished in less steps.

Multiple Pivot Sort used less number of comparisons than other sorting algorithm. The number of move and time utilization is also less than other sorting algorithm. Through different experiments in paper prove that Multiple Pivot Sort perform better on large amount of data and when data are not same means different range of data but same data type. Because of these reasons Multiple Pivot Sort is also known as general purpose sorting algorithm for many databases.

2.2 Multi-Pivot Quicksort: Theory and Experiments

It improves the Yaroslavsky dual pivot Quick sort algorithm by introducing three pivot Quick sorts. Three pivot Quick sorts perform 7-8% better than dual pivot Quick sort, and removing the extraneous effect that done in JAVA. The experiment conducted in C language. In this experiment analysis of cache behavior also conducted. We introduced three pivot p, q, r then made four list like a, b, c, d and sort the array through dual pivot concept. All values in list 'a' less than 'b' and all values in list 'b' less than 'c'. All values in list 'c' less than 'd'.

Diagram show that cache behavior of optimal three pivot quick sort is better than others. It saves all the extra iterations. Running time also depends on mechanism, so implementation in C language save iterations than Java.

2.3 Multi-Pivot Quicksort: an Experiment with Single, Dual, Triple, Quad, and Penta-Pivot Quicksort Algorithms in Python

Yaroslavsky proved dual pivot Quick sort algorithm is better than single pivot Quick sort algorithm by using JAVA virtual machine. Kushagara, Lopez-Ortiz triple pivot Quick sort algorithm works 7 - 8% better than dual pivot Quick sort algorithm. Implement different pivot algorithm like single, dual, triple, quad and penta pivot Quick sort algorithm. Finally show increase the number of pivot so, increase the performance of Quick sort algorithm.

In single pivot Quick sort algorithm select a pivot element from array. Then made two list left and right, all element greater than pivot move right side on pivot and the values less than pivot move left side on pivot. Scan the array left to right side. In dual pivot Quick sort select two pivot, first pivot must less than or equal to the second pivot.

So used three list all the element of in list 'a' less than first pivot and all elements in list 'b' less than second pivot. All remaining element placed in third list 'c'.

Apply experiment of three different type of data set by using single, double, triple, quad and penta pivot quick sort algorithm. For N=10,000 to 100,00 penta pivot Quick sort work 42% better than single pivot Quick sort algorithm. For N=100,000 to 1000,000 penta pivot Quick sort perform 48% better than single pivot Quick Sort algorithm.

For N=1000,000 to 6000,000 penta pivot Quick sort perform 61% better than single pivot Quick sort algorithm.

So, when increase the pivot the performance of Quick sort become well.

2.4 QuickSort A Historical Perspective and Empirical Study

The survey examine the study in detail all the different variations of the Quicksort starting from the original developed by Heuer in 1961 and ends with some of the latest document. It also investigated some new ones categorize algorithms and compare their performance with different versions of Quicksort. Improvements can be divided into four categories: Improvements to pivot selection, algorithms that are used another sorting algorithm is to sort specific sub lists smaller sizes, different ways to divide lists and submenus. The first category includes the original Quicksort algorithm used by Hoyer and which uses a random pivot, the Quickersort algorithm developed in 1965, which selects the pivot as the center element of the list to be sorted. Also included is the Singleton algorithm which chooses the pivot using a three-way moderator. The second category includes all the algorithms that use another sorting algorithm, insertion sort was usually the first to sort out small sub-lists of the proposed method to

improve the performance of Quicksort. The third improvement was achieved by considering the different division schematics suggested a scheme using two approaching indicators. Bentley suggested a chart where two indicators start at the left end of the list / submenu and move towards the right side. The fourth category include adaptive classification that tries to improve $O(n^2)$ behavior of Quicksort algorithm when used for sorting lists that are sorted or sorted. A new sorting algorithm is proposed based on Quicksort which uses a help group to hold array keys during sorting. No analysis or test was performed by the authors of the algorithm. The results in this paper show that SS07 requires $O(n^2)$ comparisons to sort the n items that are already sorted or sorted in reverse order. Randomized data have made $O(n \log 2n)$ comparisons.

2.5 Enhanced Quicksort Algorithm

The sorting one was a major sector for the algorithmic researchers. And much of researchers are invested to suggest more algorithm of functioning sorting. For this purpose one observed many existing algorithms of sorting

in terms of effectiveness of algorithmic complexity. One observed Quicksort to be economic and effective. The effective sorting is important to optimize the use of other algorithms that require lists together with to work correctly; it is also often inside production of the readable production for the man.

Formally, the production should meet two important conditions

- The result is in non-decreasing order.
- The result is a permutation or rearrangement of the input

Since the early beginning of calculation, sorting was considered as a fundamental problem in the study of the algorithms, that because of reasons:

- The need for matching information is essential in many applications.
- The algorithms often employ the sorting like principal sub-routine.
- Many questions of engineering come to before while putting pursuant to the algorithms from sorting.

In the algorithm that the uses divide-and-conquer the approach, it divides the problem into smaller examples of the same problem, then solves it that examples of the problem periodically (conquer), and then gathers all the solutions to obtain the principal solution for the original entry (cartel). The principle of the design of algorithm of divide-and-conquer is that it is easier to solve several small examples of a problem than a major problem. In this paper, a new algorithm of sorting is presented, called SMS-Algorithm (Scan, Move and Sort). The study proves that the algorithm proposed is more effective and faster compared to the algorithm of

Quicksort when dealing with a large size (n) of the input array. Thus, we regarded the algorithm of SMS as improvement on the algorithm of Quicksort.

The principal concept of the algorithm of SMS is elements of distributing the input array on three additional provisional arrays. Sizes of these arrays decided depending on the maximum and the values minimum of the input array. The first provisional line is called (PosArray) and contains the positive elements using the value of the element itself as its index in the array. The second line is (NegArray) what contains the elements the negative element using the absolute value of itself as its index in the array. The third array is (FreqArray) and used to save the frequent elements of the input array.

Quicksort takes time of $O(n \lg n)$ in the best algorithm of while SMS of case takes $O(N)$ complexity of time. Moreover, in the average case, the algorithm of Quicksort takes time of $O(n \lg n)$ but the algorithm of SMS takes $O(n + f * (\max + |\min|))$ time, when F is the number of frequent elements. The enhancement on the average case occurs when maximum is much of N larger than and $|\min|$, where the time complexity is close with $O(N)$. Moreover, once treated an array of the distinct elements, the algorithm of SMS was more efficient and more quickly than Quicksort. Also, in worst cases, Quicksort algorithm takes $O(N)$ time while SMS algorithm takes $O(n + f * (\max + |\min|))$. We can say that the algorithm of SMS is a faster algorithm than Quicksort by treating one of big size (N) of the input array with small values maximum and minimum of that array, in particular, if the elements are distinct.

2.6 Enhancing QuickSort Algorithm using a Dynamic Pivot Selection Technique

Quicksort intelligent algorithm based on dynamic pivot selection technique to enhance the average case and eliminate the worst algorithm behaviors. The proposed dynamic pivot selection technique relies on data to increase the chances of dividing the array or list into relatively equal volumes in order to reduce the number of repeated calls to the Quicksort algorithm.

The running time of the Quicksort algorithm depends mainly on the division of the array and the successive sub array.

If splitting leads down to a small decrease in array size or subset the runtime will be:

$$T(n) = n + T(n-c)$$

The proposed technique is designed to ensure an equal division of the matrix. Therefore, it drives the worst behavior of the case to be $O(n \log n)$. The proposed technique is also realized from an already array or sub-array that is being compared to the array elements of the axis. If the array is already classed, it will not be

processed in any other way that converts complexity $O(n^2)$ to the best behavior of the algorithm state; that is, $O(n)$.

In order to determine the pivot of recursive calls the next level, the correct mean of the values is greater than the pivot as the pivot value of the recursive call of the right sub-array. Similarly, the correct mean of values below the pivot is passed as the pivot value of the recursive call of the left sub-array. This pivot selection technique helps to divide the array into almost equal halves, improving the efficiency of the Quicksort algorithm. Using dynamic pivot selection technology, the worst case scenario in the Quicksort Model algorithm is converted to the best case of the MQuicksort algorithm with $\theta(n)$ runtime requirements. The MQuicksort algorithm works with $\theta(n \log n)$ in the worst case confirmed by experiments.

2.7 MQ Sort an Innovative Algorithm using Quick Sort and Merge Sort

MQSort includes all the best features of these Merge Sort and Quick sort algorithms resulting in the reduction of time complexity which is the main factor to determine the good sorting algorithm)

A sorting algorithm performs swapping and compression operation. Different types of algorithm are use Bubble sort Quick sort Heap sort Merge sort etc But their efficiency depend on the number of input or the problem line. Here we discuss the Quick sort and Merge sort and develop the new algorithm MQ Sort. Quick sort developed by Hoare this is the one of the best internal sorting algorithm. It use Divide and conquer approach In this approach its divide the array in two sub array for this its select a random number as a pivot and sort the element in such a way all small element are in left side and greater are in right side and this function recursively call until the given array completely sort It's expected running time is $O(n \log n)$ and the constant factors hidden in $O(n \log n)$ are small. It's also having the advantage of sorting in place and it works well in virtual memory environments. The main disadvantage of the quick sort is it reaches the on worst case on that data set which is common in use. These are the action perform on the given list All items less than the pivot element. The pivot element is place on final place All items greater than the pivot element At this point the pivot element in its final place and quick sort will be applied recursively to The sequence is sorted when the recursion terminates. Merge sort is good for where given data is too big to have in memory ,Because it star data in regular It use fewer comparison as compared to heap sort Merge sort work as fellow If the list is of length 0 or 1, then it is already sorted. Otherwise. Divide the unsorted list into two sub lists of about half the size. Sort Lomuto algorithm it iterates whole array and swap

each sub list recursively by merge sort algorithm. Merge the two sub lists back into one sorted.

2.8 Performance Analysis of Merge Sort and Quick Sort: MQSORT

A sorting algorithm performs swapping and compression operation. Different types of algorithm are use Bubble sort Quick sort Heap sort Merge sort etc But their efficiency depend on the number of input or the problem line. Here we discuss the Quick sort and Merge sort and develop the new algorithm MQ Sort. Quick sort developed by Hoare this is the one of the best internal sorting algorithm. It use Divide and conquer approach In this approach its divide the array in two sub array for this its select a random number as a pivot and sort the element in such a way all small element are in left side and greater are in right side and this function recursively call until the given array completely sort It's expected running time is $O(n \log n)$ and the constant factors hidden in $O(n \log n)$ are small. It's also having the advantage of sorting in place and it works well in virtual memory environments. The main disadvantage of the quick sort is it reaches the on worst case on that data set which is common in use. These are the action perform on the given list All items less than the pivot element. The pivot element is place on final place All items greater than the pivot element At this point the pivot element in its final place and quick sort will be applied recursively to The sequence is sorted when the recursion terminates. Merge sort is good for where given data is too big to have in memory ,Because it star data in regular It use fewer comparison as compared to heap sort Merge sort work as fellow If the list is of length 0 or 1, then it is already sorted. Otherwise. Divide the unsorted list into two sub lists of about half the size. Sort each sub list recursively by merge sort algorithm. Merge the two sub lists back into one sorted.

2.9 Hybrid Quicksort : AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

Quicksort is widely used algorithm in sorting big data due to its easiness, less processing and fast output with $n \log(n)$ throughput. Quicksort divides array in two parts and process both separately and so on. This paper's basic idea is to study performance improvement with multiple partitions on quicksort with different hybrid approaches.

A hybrid approach uses cut of to shell sort for small data key. It also describes the performance of existing algorithms, compare to different hybrid approached and new hybrid algorithm.

Existing algorithms:

Hoare Algorithm it choses first key as pivot and than moves smaller keys its left or greater to right. At end it returns correct pivot to partition data in 2 parts.

smaller elements when pivot found. Modified Lomuto directly modified array in iteration without doing a swap in start. In Median of five, Pivot is Sample of 5 size elements: first, last, center, center of start and center and center of the center. Sorted sample used as pivot. In three-way partitioning, data set up in 3 partitions based on four indexes, less than, equals to, and greater than. It moves all elements that are equal to the pivot in place.

Proposed hybrid Algorithms:

It uses existing algorithms with cut of to shellsort algorithm between array size of 6 and 32. Shellsort is enhancement of insertion sort, It divide the array into multiple sub arrays and sort all using insertion sort. Following is the proposed algorithm. It gets cutoff using shellsort:

```
Void sortHF(int *data, int first , int last , int,int  
(*v)(int*,int,int), int cutoff)  
{  
    if(frst < last)  
    {  
        if(last - frst <= cutoff)  
        {  
            shell(data, frst, last); return;  
        }  
        int pv = v(data, frst, last);  
        sortF(data, frst,pv-1, v);  
        sortF(data, pv+1, last, v);  
    }  
}
```

Testing and results:

After studying proposed algorithm on range 10000 to 100000. Algorithm used to sort 5 unique and duplicate sequences of random numbers of specific size with time calculation.

The best results for unique numbers are following:

- Hoare using cutoff of 30 in 146.82ms
- Modified Hoare using cutoff of 19 in 181.86ms
- Median-of-five with cutoff of 11 in 182.8ms

The best results for duplicate numbers are following:

- Hoare using cutoff of 29 in 174.34ms
- Modified Hoare using cutoff of 22 in 140.62ms
- Median-of-five with cutoff of 27 in 149.06ms

From above study for the best output in duplicate sequences we can use Modified Lumoto with cutoff value of 22 elements and in unique sequences modified Hoare with cutoff value of 30 elements.

3. Discussion

Quick sort algorithm was introduced by Hoare in 1961. Its time complexity for average case is $O(n \log n)$ and for worst case is $O(n^2)$. The worst case scenario narrowly occur, mostly problem are solved through average case, that's why Quick sort is best choice for sorting the large array. In 2009, Yaroslavsky introduced dual pivot Quick sort algorithm. It used two pivot and three list for sorting

array and take less time than single pivot Quick sort. So, performance of Quick sort increased. In 2013, Kushagra S, Lopiz-Ortiz further modify dual pivot Quick sort algorithm by three, four and five pivot. Then experiment conducted on different size of data set. When used 6M random items in experiment. The penta pivot Quick sort algorithm performs 61% better than single pivot Quick sort algorithm. So, increased the number of pivot then less number of iteration consumed that's why Multi-Pivot Quick sort algorithm perform well than simple Quick sort. When sort huge array then Multi-Pivot Quick sort is best selection. The cache behavior in C language is better than Java.

Quick sort algorithm, sort the large array very efficiently. But we save time through some changing in Quick sort. When array contain values that are duplicated, Quick sort take normal time. Hybrid Quick sort algorithm save time and number of iterations. When values comes in foam of duplication. When our data set is very large then enhanced Quick Sort algorithm takes less time than simple Quick Sort Algorithm. Enhanced Quick Sort algorithm used the concept of SMS (Scan, Move, and Sort). So, large data set sort easily and less time consume, because less number of iteration execute. Multiple pivot sort algorithm resolve many issues in Quick sort algorithm. Multiple pivot sort algorithm select multiple pivot from large array. If some pivots are same then same pivot placed in series. It handles the repetition of values easily and sort the repeated values in few steps. Finally, we increase the performance of Quick sort by introducing the Multiple pivot sort, enhanced Quick sort and Hybrid Quick sort algorithm.

4. Advantages

Quick sort is best sorting algorithm, when our data set is large. It is in place sorting algorithm that means no extra memory requiring when sorting the array. When we sorting the array, mostly average case apply and Quick sort time complexity in average case is $O(n \log n)$. Quick sort very efficient used the space. When speed is our necessary focus then Quick sort is best choice, because its performance is high. Quick sort is easily implemented and compatible with internal mechanism of computer memory. Quick sort not require merging like other divide and concur algorithm Merge sort, so sorting easily and timely done. Quick sort gave good result than Merge sort when implemented on huge data set. Quick sort is cache friendly algorithm.

5. Disadvantages

Quick sort time complexity for worst case is $O(n^2)$. If the array already sorted then Bubble sort is best choice then Quick sort. It is faster on some data set, not for all categories of data. If any small problem occur then it is very difficult to resolve.

Paper Title	Performance	Objective	Conclusion
Multiple Pivot Sort Algorithm is faster than Quicksort Algorithm: An Empirical Study	Performance better than simple Quick Sort and used less number of operation than average case of Quick Sort $O(n \log n)$.	To increase the performance of Quick sort algorithm by using multiple pivot that gave better results than merge sort and heap sort.	Multi pivot quicksort algorithm used less number of iterations for sorting the array.
Multi-Pivot Quicksort: Theory and Experiments	3 Pivot performances are better than 7-8% than 2 pivots.	To improve the dual pivot Quick sort by three pivot and remove extraneous effect and provide good cache behavior.	Improve the Yaroslavsky dual pivot Quicksort algorithm and introduce three pivot Quick sort that perform 7-8% better than dual pivot Quick sort.
Multi-Pivot Quicksort: an Experiment with Single, Dual, Triple, Quad, and Penta-Pivot Quicksort Algorithms in Python	For 6M random inputs, penta pivot works 61% better than single pivot Quick Sort.	To increase the number of pivot then increase the quicksort algorithm performance for when sorting the large array.	Experiment run on different size of inputs, when apply on 6M inputs, penta pivot algorithm work 61% better than single pivot Quick sort.
QuickSort: A Historical Perspective and Empirical Study	Compare different sorting algorithms and their performance varies on different scenarios	To examines the details of different versions of quicksort from inventions of quicksort to current version. Investigates some new sorting algorithms and compares their performances to the various Versions.	Comparison between different sorting algorithm and prove quick sort is better than others for large data.
Enhanced Quicksort Algorithm	QuickSort takes 425 ms for sorting and SMS algorithm takes 259 ms.	To enhance the Quicksort algorithm in the best, average, and worst cases when an input array of a large size and when the maximum and the minimum values were small, especially when sorting a list of discrete elements	A new sorting algorithm is presented called SMS (Scan, Move, Sort), this algorithm divided the array into three parts positive, negative, and frequent elements, and moved each element into its correct place in a single pass
Enhancing QuickSort Algorithm using a Dynamic Pivot Selection Technique	For array size 100000 QuickSort with last pivot takes 52.3214 ms and MQuickSort takes 46.852 ms	To enhance quicksort algorithm that includes dynamic pivot selection technique to improve average case and exclude the worst case behaviors of the algorithm	Introduce new algorithm called (MQuickSort) built on a dynamic pivot selection technique. In order to determine the pivots for the next level recursive calls, the integer average of the values larger than the pivot is passed as the pivot value of the recursive call for the right sub array.

<p>MQ Sort an Innovative Algorithm using Quick Sort and Merge Sort</p>	<p>For worst case MQ Sort T.C is $O(n \log n)$.</p>	<p>To prove that MQ Sort an Innovative Algorithm using Quick Sort and Merge Sort. Data is sorting in ascending or descending order.</p>	<p>The time complexity of MQ Sort in average case is $O(n \log n)$ that apply on many cases. Worst case normally not used.</p>
<p>HYBRID QUICKSORT: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY</p>	<p>Hybrid modified Lomuto partition algorithm and cutoff value of 22 elements for the best average running time.</p>	<p>To increase performance improvement with multiple partitions on quicksort with different hybrid approach.</p>	<p>The best output in duplicate sequences we can use Modified Lumoto with cutoff value of 22 elements and in unique sequences modified Hoare with cutoff value of 30 elements.</p>

6. Conclusion

Quick sort algorithm works well on huge data set, normally average case apply and its time complexity is reasonable. Some changed in Quick sort increase the performance. Multiple pivot sort, Hybrid Quick sort and Enhanced Quick sort algorithm resolve the issues and increase the performance of Quick sort algorithm. Quick sort require no extra memory for sorting and cache friendly algorithm.

7. Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Dr. Muhammad Aasim Qureshi for support and gave knowledge for the relevant field. We also thanks to Thomas H Cormen and reference paper researcher.

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